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tensions between autonomy and competitiveness*

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Digital sovereignty in an 'open manner'? EU tensions between autonomy and competitiveness

Edoardo Celeste, Victor Henriquez Diaz and Elio Machado Neto¹

Abstract

At the end of 2022, the EU solemnly adopted the Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles, a non-legally binding document systematising the Union's shared political intentions and commitments towards the digital transformation. The Declaration stresses the importance of achieving a sufficient level of strategic autonomy in the digital field vis-a-vis foreign countries. This idea is expressed using the concept of 'digital sovereignty in an open manner', intended as a strategy to improve independence from non-EU players while fostering 'the availability of services' and 'a dynamic, resource efficient, and fair economy' (Recital 6). This chapter identifies a tension between these policy objectives. Is it possible for the EU to become digitally independent while maintaining its founding vision of an open and competitive economy? The chapter aims to assess this EU policy ambition by contextualising it in the existing regulatory framework and by carrying out a comparative analysis of similar policies emerging in the US and China. The chapter concludes proposing the adoption of a necessity and proportionality test to avoid protectionist distortions and to assess the alignment of EU digital sovereignty strategies with the protection of fundamental rights.

Keywords: digital sovereignty; open strategic autonomy; competitiveness; protectionism.

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I. Introduction

In recent years, the term ‘digital sovereignty’ permeated the European Union’s political discussions and actions concerning the quest for building an ‘Europe fit for the digital age’. The digital sovereignty discourse also promotes the importance of achieving the EU strategic autonomy in the digital field vis-a-vis foreign countries combined with a reaffirmed commitment to fundamental rights protection and the green transition. The EU Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles, adopted at the end of 2022, systematised the Union’s shared political intentions and commitments towards the digital transformation. In this document, digital sovereignty is explicitly presented as one of the pillars of what is defined as the ‘EU way for the digital transformation’ (Recital 6). The Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 (Decision (EU) 2022/2481) stressed the importance of a secure, resilient, performant, and sustainable digital infrastructure. The EU planned to achieve at least 20% of world production in value of cutting-edge semiconductors (Article 4 of the Decision), doubling its current share of the global market. The European Chips Act entered into force in September 2023, setting a legal framework for the EU’s ambition to reduce its external dependencies in that specific sector.

The Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles promotes the idea of supporting digital sovereignty in an ‘open manner’ as a strategy to improve, among other aspects, ‘the availability of services’ and ‘contribute to a dynamic, resource efficient, and fair economy and society in the EU’ (Recital 6). This chapter identifies a tension between EU digital sovereignty strategies and these two policy objectives. Is it really possible for the EU to become digitally independent while maintaining its founding vision of an open and competitive economy? The chapter aims to assess this EU policy ambition by contextualising it in the existing regulatory framework and by carrying out a comparative analysis of similar policies emerging in the US and China.

Firstly, the chapter will reconstruct the policy strategy adopted by the EU in the digital field, showing how digital sovereignty objectives have surfaced only in the last few years in response to geopolitical developments. The third section will analyse the text of the recently adopted EU Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles. We will highlight the tension between the stated objective of pursuing digital sovereignty ‘in an open manner’ and that of guaranteeing a ‘resource efficient and fair’ economy. The fourth section of the chapter will contextualise these ambitions in the existing or planned EU regulatory framework in the digital field. It will provide an overview of the status of digital dependence that currently characterises the EU and will illustrate the recent shift from a regulatory strategy centred on extending the EU regulatory influence on third countries to one aiming to reattract resources and the production of digital goods on EU soil. The fifth section will perform a comparative analysis of analogous strategies in the US and China, showing the emergence of common trends. The final section will conclude that EU strategies share similar justifications and may lead to distortive protectionist effects. We argue that the EU should carefully assess the medium to long term objectives of its digital sovereignty strategies. The protection of fundamental rights should serve as a guiding principle to assess whether EU regulatory measures go beyond their primary objective and risk to create distortive economic effects. A necessity and proportionality test is recommended to identify suitable solutions in line with EU aims and values.

II. The EU policy strategy: from smart growth to digital strategic autonomy

A. First decade (2010-2020): Smart growth

We can divide the history of EU digital policy strategies into two periods: a first decade going from 2010 to 2020, and the current decade, from 2020 to 2030, which has been dubbed the ‘digital decade’. The first decade saw the adoption by the EU Commission of the first EU Digital Agenda, which encompasses a series of initiatives.² The Digital Agenda recognised for the first time the important role that Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) play towards achieving EU goals. According to the Commission, the ICTs sector represented 5% of the European GDP and possessed a positive overall impact on productivity growth.³ The Agenda highlighted key action areas for the EU: it aimed to foster sustainable socioeconomic development for a vibrant and secure a digital single market built on fast Internet access and interoperability. The Agenda was one of the flagship initiatives of the Europe 2020 Strategy launched in March 2010 by the European Commission. The 2020 Strategy established three intertwined priorities: smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.⁴ The Agenda possessed both an inward and an outward looking dimension: on the one hand, it aimed to foster digitalisation of public and private institutions within the EU, and, on the other hand, it sought to transform the EU economy in order to be able to compete on the global market.⁵

In 2015, the EU adopted the Digital Single Market Strategy, which capitalised on the objectives established by the 2010 Digital Agenda recognising the then already ubiquitous presence of ICTs in all economic sectors.⁶ The Strategy was built on three pillars: better access for consumers and businesses to online goods and services across Europe by breaking down barriers to cross-border online activities; creating the right conditions for digital networks and services to develop high-speed and secure infrastructures; and maximising the EU growth potential by investing in research and innovation.⁷

During the first decade, the EU focused its action on eliminating internal barriers and finally achieve a true digital EU single market. The Digital Agenda for Europe and the Digital Single Market Strategy do not mention digital sovereignty or autonomy, reliance or dependence. Despite the EU’s stated objective of maintaining its leading position in the digital sector, this theme will progressively emerge only in subsequent years.⁸

B) Second decade (2020-2030): Digital strategic autonomy

By the end of the 2010’s, making Europe fit for the digital age had become one of the priorities of the Commission. EU policy documents consecrate the years 2020-2030 as the

² European Commission, Communication “A Digital Agenda for Europe”, COM(2010)245.

³ Ibid, 3.

⁴ European Commission, Communication ‘Europe 2020 A Strategy For Smart, Sustainable And Inclusive Growth’ COM(2010)2020.

⁵ See Małgorzata Stec and Mariola Grzebyk, ‘The Implementation of the Strategy Europe 2020 Objectives in European Union Countries: The Concept Analysis and Statistical Evaluation’, *Quality & Quantity* 52, no. 1 (1 January 2018): 119–33, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-016-0454-7>.

⁶ European Commission, Communication ‘A Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe’, COM/2015/0192 final.

⁷ Ibid; see also Charles A. Weiss, ‘Available to All, Produced By Few: The Economic and Cultural Impact of Europe’s Digital Single Market Strategy Within The Audiovisual Industry’, *Columbia Business Law Review* 2016, no. 3 (2016): 878–923, <https://doi.org/10.7916/cblr.v2016i3.1749>.

⁸ European Commission, ‘A Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe’, 3.

European ‘Digital Decade’.⁹ Achieving a ‘smart growth’, however, is now more linked to environmental concerns, mainly focused on the EU plans to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.¹⁰ For the first time, the EU also sets out more explicitly its willingness to play a stronger role from a geopolitical perspective.¹¹ Only in this context, the Commission started focusing on strengthening EU digital sovereignty.

We cannot find a univocal definition of digital sovereignty neither in academic articles nor in policy instruments.¹² One of the reasons that can explain the nebulousness of this concept lies in the very fact that the concept of ‘sovereignty’ has hardly been neatly defined.¹³ Digital sovereignty is the latest concept emerged from the application of the traditional notion of sovereignty to the digital ecosystem. The expression ‘technological sovereignty’ already emerged in the 1960’s.¹⁴ ‘Data sovereignty’ was the most common concept at academic and commercial level, although it is now perceived to be a specific subset of the notion of digital sovereignty.¹⁵ Such an evolution should not surprise as it reflects the perception of technological changes in the contemporary society.¹⁶

Digital sovereignty claims at EU level emerge from the need to ‘control the digital’, indented by the ecosystem encompassing data, infrastructures, software, hardware and services which represent the pillars of the digital society.¹⁷ Such ‘control’ of the digital ecosystem consists in the possibility to apply EU values and rules to digital assets. However, that regulatory power, to be effective, presupposes a status of relative strategic autonomy of the EU in the digital field. For example, the EU can well decide to unilaterally apply its law beyond EU borders, but the fact that data might be processed by non-EU companies or physically stored in third countries may reduce the effective capacity of the EU to fully control such data, for the mere fact that it might be simultaneously subject to a concurrent sovereign power of another jurisdiction.¹⁸

⁹ See European Commission, Communication ‘2030 Digital Compass: The European Way For The Digital Decade, COM(2021) 118 Final’.

¹⁰ European Commission, Communication ‘The European Green Deal’ COM/2019/640 final.

¹¹ European Commission, ‘Priorities 2019-2024’, accessed 21 September 2023, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024_en.

¹² Edoardo Celeste, ‘Digital Sovereignty in the EU: Challenges and Future Perspectives’, in *Data Protection Beyond Borders: Transatlantic Perspectives on Extraterritoriality and Sovereignty*, ed. Federico Fabbrini, Edoardo Celeste, and John Quinn (Oxford: Hart Publishing (Bloomsbury), 2021), 211–28.

¹³ See Hent Kalmo and Quentin Skinner, eds., *Sovereignty in Fragments: The Past, Present and Future of a Contested Concept* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010).

¹⁴ Stephane Couture and Sophie Toupin, ‘What Does the Notion of “Sovereignty” Mean When Referring to the Digital?’, *New Media & Society* 21, no. 10 (1 October 2019): 2305–22, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444819865984>.

¹⁵ Ibid; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi), ‘Project GAIA-X – A Federated Data Infrastructure as the Cradle of a Vibrant European Ecosystem’, October 2019, https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/EN/Publikationen/Digitale-Welt/project-gaia-x.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4.

¹⁶ See, e.g., in relation to the concept of digital constitutionalism, Edoardo Celeste, ‘The Scope of Application of Digital Constitutionalism. Output from an Empirical Research’ (Nexa Research Papers 2017) Nexa Research Papers, <https://nexa.polito.it/nexacenterfiles/E.%20Celeste%20-%20Research%20Paper.pdf>.

¹⁷ See Luciano Floridi, ‘The Fight for Digital Sovereignty: What It Is, and Why It Matters, Especially for the EU’, *Philosophy & Technology* 33, no. 3 (1 September 2020): 369–78, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-020-00423-6>; Patrik Hummel et al., ‘Data Sovereignty: A Review’, *Big Data & Society* 8, no. 1 (1 January 2021): 2053951720982012, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720982012>.

¹⁸ On this topic see Fabbrini Federico et al., *Data Protection beyond Borders: Transatlantic Perspectives on Extraterritoriality and Sovereignty*, Paperback edition. (Oxford: Hart, 2022).

Such a circumstance led the EU to implement two simultaneous types of digital sovereignty strategies.¹⁹ On the one hand, the EU has tried to reinforce its digital sovereignty in a centripetal way. In other words, by exercising a regulatory force that reattracts digital assets within EU borders. For example, when the Court of Justice of the EU required metadata stored by telecommunication operators to be conserved within the EU.²⁰ On the other hand, the EU has implemented regulatory strategies to secure its digital sovereignty in a centrifugal way, meaning by extending its regulatory reach beyond its boundaries. Here, an apparent example being the notorious extraterritorial scope of application of the General Data Protection Regulation.²¹

In 2020, the EU Commission adopted the communication *Shaping Europe's Digital Future*. Beside stressing that green and digital transformation should go hand in hand, this document also presents 'technological sovereignty' as 'Europe's ability to define its own rules and values in the digital age' based on its autonomous development and deployment of its own digital capacities (data infrastructure, networks and communications), thus reducing dependence on other global players.²² In this document it is therefore apparent how the dimension of strategic autonomy started to emerge as a necessary requirement to achieve a full control on digital assets. The document highlights that this approach does not aim to penalise any international actor, but prioritizes Europeans' needs and values.²³ To this end, the Commission identifies a series of key objectives to build 'a European society powered by digital solutions that are strongly rooted in [European] common values': technology that works for people; a fair and competitive economy; an open democratic and sustainable society; and Europe as a global player.²⁴ Similarly, a 2020 European Parliament brief highlighted that the concept of 'digital sovereignty' recently surfaced as 'a means of promoting the notion of European leadership and strategic autonomy in the digital field'.²⁵

In 2021, the Commission released the 2030 Digital Compass.²⁶ This communication established the European cardinal points for the digital decade: a digitally skilled population and highly skilled digital professionals; secure and performant sustainable digital infrastructures; digital transformation of businesses and digitalisation of public services. This document was complemented in December 2022 by the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030.²⁷ Article 1 establishes that such a programme aims to create the right environment

¹⁹ See Celeste, 'Digital Sovereignty in the EU: Challenges and Future Perspectives'; Edoardo Celeste, 'Brexit and the Risks of Digital Sovereignism' in Edoardo Celeste and others (eds), *Data protection and digital sovereignty post-Brexit* (Hart 2023). Edoardo Celeste, 'Brexit and the Risks of Digital Sovereignism', in *Data Protection and Digital Sovereignty Post-Brexit*, ed. Edoardo Celeste et al. (Oxford: Hart, 2023), 181–98.

²⁰ *Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others*, No. Joined Cases C-293/12 and C-594/12 (ECJ 8 April 2014); Edoardo Celeste, 'The Court of Justice and the Ban on Bulk Data Retention: Expansive Potential and Future Scenarios', *European Constitutional Law Review* 15, no. 1 (March 2019): 134–57, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1574019619000038>; cf. national data localisation laws in . Edoardo Celeste and Federico Fabbrini, 'Competing Jurisdictions: Data Privacy across the Borders', in *Data Privacy and Trust in Cloud Computing*, ed. Theo Lynn et al. (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2020), 43–58.

²¹ See Federico Fabbrini and Edoardo Celeste, 'The Right to Be Forgotten in the Digital Age: The Challenges of Data Protection Beyond Borders', *German Law Journal* 21, no. S1 (March 2020): 55–65, <https://doi.org/10.1017/glj.2020.14>.

²² European Commission, Communication 'Shaping Europe's Digital Future' COM(2020) 67 final 2.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Madiaga Tambiana, 'Digital Sovereignty for Europe' (European Parliamentary Research Service, July 2020), [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651992/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)651992_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651992/EPRS_BRI(2020)651992_EN.pdf), 1.

²⁶ European Commission, 'Priorities 2019-2024'.

²⁷ 'Decision (EU) 2022/2481 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 Establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030', 323 OJ L § (2022), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dec/2022/2481/oj/eng>.

through cooperation between EU institutions and Member States to foster innovation and investment for the delivery of the digital targets at Union level by 2030.²⁸ Additionally, Recital 1 stresses that such an environment should empower citizens and businesses through digital transformation, which encompasses ‘digital sovereignty in an open manner, respect for fundamental rights, the rule of law and democracy, inclusion, accessibility, equality, sustainability, resilience, security, improving quality of life, the availability of services and respect for citizens’ rights and aspirations’.²⁹ Words that, as we will see, will be reiterated verbatim in the Preamble of the EU Declaration of Digital Rights and Principles.

In the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 the objective of reaching digital strategic autonomy is apparent. Besides a digitally skilled population and the digitalisation of public services and businesses, the document sets as a target the implementation of ‘secure, resilient, performant and sustainable digital infrastructures’.³⁰ Such a target would aim to exercise a centripetal force vis-à-vis key digital assets. In particular, it aims to foster the capillary introduction of fixed and mobile high-speed networks, reaching at least 20% of the global production of semiconductors, fully in compliance with the EU sustainability targets; achieve an even distribution of a significant number of climate neutral edge nodes around the Union, and successfully launch a performing quantum computer by 2025.³¹

Digital sovereignty positioned itself at the centre of a broader strategic autonomy strategy for the EU.³² In the 2021 Strategic Foresight Report, the EU Commission identified challenging areas that the EU would have to address to ensure the bloc’s ‘freedom to act’.³³ It recognized the necessity to support human-centred technology to be digitally sovereign.³⁴ But, more interestingly, three of the critical areas identified in the path to open strategic autonomy involve a close integration with digital sovereignty. The Report acknowledged that in order to be digitally sovereign, it is essential to strengthen the EU capacity to store, extract and process data in observance of fundamental rights.³⁵ In this area, as previously mentioned, the main challenge is the vast amount of data stored and processed in cloud services offered by non-EU cloud storage providers, resulting in a strategic dependency for the EU.³⁶ Likewise, the EU Commission acknowledged the urgent need to invest in the development and production of next generation technologies and semiconductors chips, as limited production could disrupt the supply chain and affect business continuity of key industries. The EU Commission stressed the importance of critical raw materials for the green transition and the defence industry. Raw materials coming from non-EU countries are essential for wind and solar power, electric vehicles batteries, aircraft production and small drones. Hence the need to build an intersectoral international partnership of industrial, research and trade policies to secure stable and diverse supply.

In the subsequent 2022 Strategic Foresight Report, aware of the shifting geopolitical scenario, the EU Commission deepened its vision on the Twin Transition. It continued to highlight the relevance of developing domestic capacities and diversifying the sources of supply of critical commodities as a mechanism to reduce the existing strategic dependencies

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid, art 4(2).

³¹ Ibid.

³² Cristiano Cagnin et al., ‘Shaping and Securing the EU’s Open Strategic Autonomy by 2040 and Beyond’ (Luxemburg: European Commission - Joint Research Centre, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.2760/414963>, 23.

³³ See European Commission, 2021 Strategic Foresight Report ‘The EU’s capacity and freedom to act’ COM(2021)750 final, 1.

³⁴ Ibid, 3.

³⁵ Ibid, 10.

³⁶ Ibid, 11.

from foreign providers.³⁷ Additionally, the 2022 Report made a call for additional investment in research and innovation across critical technologies as this would strengthen the EU's resilience towards the twin transitions.³⁸ Similarly, the 2023 Strategic Foresight Report reiterated the areas of action to secure the EU open strategic autonomy, mindful of the rising competition for influence among nations.³⁹ Overcoming current dependencies across sectors - including technology - by leveraging the Single Market is a key element for the EU Commission in order to achieve strategic autonomy.⁴⁰ Thus the encouragement to use trade defence instruments, regulation on foreign subsidies and procurement.⁴¹ Likewise, it reiterated the need for support for the manufacturing of raw materials that are important for energy transition.⁴²

III. The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles

A. Internal objectives and international ambitions

The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade was adopted in December 2022 after an agreement was reached among the EU Commission, European Parliament, and the Council.⁴³ The Declaration is not legally binding and does not affect existing legal rules and their application.⁴⁴ It is organised into six chapters that cover respectively: a human-centric approach; solidarity and inclusion; freedom of choice; digital participation; safety, security and empowerment; and sustainability.⁴⁵ The dispositions of the Declaration can be classified into three groups: a) rights, identified by the expression 'everyone has the right to'; b) principles using a performative present tense; and c) principles using a conditional tense 'should', including more ambitious statements.⁴⁶

According to its Preamble, the Declaration should build on existing EU law. The rights mentioned in the Declaration are already protected by the existing legal framework.⁴⁷ Cocito and de Hert speak of a 'normative equivalency paradigm', which is the approach adopted by the United Nations (UN) over human rights on the Internet.⁴⁸ Recital 3 of the Preamble would support this view by expressing that European values and fundamental rights

³⁷ See European Commission, 2022 Strategic Foresight Report 'Twinning the green and digital transitions in the new geopolitical context' (2022) COM(2022)289 final, 13

³⁸ Ibid, 14.

³⁹ European Commission, 2023 Strategic Foresight Report 'Sustainability and people's wellbeing at the heart of Europe's Open Strategic Autonomy' COM(2023)376 final, 2.

⁴⁰ Ibid, 14.

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Ibid, 15.

⁴³ 'European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade', OJ C 23/01 § (2023).

⁴⁴ Recital 10.

⁴⁵ See Alba Perez Victorio, Edoardo Celeste, and Alberto Quintavalla, 'Greening AI? The New Principle of Sustainable Digital Products and Services in the EU', *Common Market Law Review* 61, no. 4 (1 August 2024).

⁴⁶ Edoardo Celeste, 'Digital Constitutionalism, EU Digital Sovereignty Ambitions and the Role of the European Declaration on Digital Rights', in *New Directions in Digitalisation. European Union and Its Neighbours in a Globalized World*, ed. Annegret Engel, Xavier Groussot, and Gunnar Thor Petursson, vol. 13 (Switzerland: Springer Nature, 2024), 255–71; Cristina Cocito and Paul De Hert, 'The Transformative Nature of the EU Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles: Replacing the Old Paradigm (Normative Equivalency of Rights)', *Computer Law & Security Review* 50 (1 September 2023): 105846, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2023.105846> who speak of a 'mixed' or 'hybrid' normative nature of the Declaration.

⁴⁷ Maksymilian Kuźmicz, 'European or Universal? The European Declaration of Digital Rights in a Global Context', International Conference on Computer Ethics 1, no. 1 (10 May 2023), <https://soremo.library.iit.edu/index.php/CEPE2023/article/view/250>.

⁴⁸ Cocito and De Hert, 'The Transformative Nature of the EU Declaration on Digital Rights'.

applicable offline should be applied in the digital environment. Yet, despite its explicit intentions, the nature of the Declaration is not completely declaratory and ancillary to existing EU law. This document often carries out a process of ‘normative retrofitting’: it makes explicit principles that guide or underpin existing or planned regulatory instruments of the EU in the digital field.⁴⁹ Thus, appearing to be in line with the phenomenon of ‘digital constitutionalism’, which has witnessed the emergence of a significant number of digital charters and declarations articulating rights and principles for the digital society.⁵⁰

From an internal point of view, the Declaration emerged from the perceived necessity for the European Union to adapt its values and fundamental rights to the digital environment.⁵¹ It systematises the Union’s shared ‘political intentions and commitments’ towards the digital transformation.⁵² The Declaration can be perceived as a synthesis of guiding principles of the EU digital agenda encompassing elements of the Digital Single Market communication and the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. According to the Preamble, the Declaration should be taken as a reference point for policymakers as well as for companies operating in the digital field.⁵³

Beside this first category of aims of the Declaration, which are more related to the internal dimension of the EU, it is also possible to identify a second mission of this document, which is more outward-looking, focusing on the role of EU digital rights and principles on the international plane. In this regard, one can consider the Declaration as the EU’s contribution to the Global Digital Compact, the initiative launched by the United Nations which aims to establish a set of shared principles for an ‘open, free and secure digital future for all’ by 2024.⁵⁴ This convergence between EU strategies and this UN project can be seen as a further way to legitimise EU’s actions in the international arena, by contextualising EU principles a in the broader internal policy framework. Indeed, the Declaration also possesses an explicit ‘soft power’ role.⁵⁵ Recital 11 of the Preamble stresses that the EU should use the Declaration as a tool to promote its conception of digital rights and principles also in the context of its international relations. The ambition of the EU is to spread a human centric and fundamental rights-based model for the development of the digital society. The EU adopted the Declaration with the intent to use it as a brief and succinct policy document with a quasi-constitutional language, which would ‘guide’ international partners and businesses and influence their approach to the digital transformation.⁵⁶

⁴⁹ See Perez Victorio, Celeste, and Quintavalla, ‘Greening AI?’ and Celeste ‘Digital Constitutionalism’.

⁵⁰ Celeste, ‘Digital Constitutionalism, EU Digital Sovereignty Ambitions and the Role of the European Declaration on Digital Rights’; more generally on this phenomenon, see Edoardo Celeste, *Digital Constitutionalism: The Role of Internet Bills of Rights* (London: Routledge, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003256908>; Edoardo Celeste, ‘Internet Bills of Rights: Generalisation and Re-Specification Towards a Digital Constitution’, *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies* 30, no. 2 (September 2023): 25–54, <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/916450>.

⁵¹ See Recitals 3 and 7.

⁵² Recital 7.

⁵³ Respectively, Recital 7 and 8.

⁵⁴ European Union Foreign Affairs Council, ‘European Contribution to the Global Digital Compact’, March 2023, https://www.eeas.europa.eu/delegations/un-new-york/global-digital-compact-bold-step-towards-digital-transformation_en?s=63; United Nations General Assembly, Resolution No. A/RES/76/307, Modalities for the Summit of the Future (2022), <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n22/587/47/pdf/n2258747.pdf>.

⁵⁵ Cf. Anu Bradford, *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World* (London: Oxford University Press, 2020).

⁵⁶ Recital 11.

B. Digital sovereignty ‘in an open manner’ vs a ‘resource efficient and fair’ economy

Recital 6 of the Declaration’s Preamble states that the EU model for the digital transition ‘encompasses in particular *digital sovereignty in an open manner*, respect for fundamental rights, rule of law and democracy’, adding that this approach ‘should contribute to a dynamic, *resource efficient, and fair economy* and society in the EU.’⁵⁷ The Declaration does not define the exact meaning of the expression ‘digital sovereignty in an open manner’, nor how a similar concept could be reconciled with a ‘dynamic, resource efficient, and fair economy’. This chapter identifies a tension between these two concepts and policy objectives. Digital sovereignty emerges in the EU also as a tool to achieve strategic autonomy. The EU, in order to control its digital assets, put in motion a policy and regulatory strategy that exercises a centripetal force. In the previous section, we have seen how the EU is heavily investing in digital infrastructures for the EU territory, which aim to support the digital transition within the Union. This chapter questions how enhancing the EU strategic autonomy by reattracting digital assets and services in the EU could be effectively achieved in an open manner and in a way that would be compatible with a fair economy based on an efficient use of resources. In this section, we start tackling this question by analysing the meaning of the expressions ‘digital sovereignty in an open manner’ and ‘resource efficient and fair economy’, and recontextualising them in the current EU regulatory and policy framework.

In the 2020 communication *Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*, the EU Commission stated that technological sovereignty consists in the EU capacity to ‘define its own rules and values in the digital age’.⁵⁸ Such an objective requires the EU to be able to control its digital infrastructures and guarantee their resilience. In order to do so, the communication highlights that reducing the EU dependency from external actors is crucial. Yet, this economic intervention in the digital market is not seen as discriminatory, targeting any other commercial player, nor is regarded as anticompetitive, as is justified by the need to preserve EU fundamental rights and principles in the digital ecosystem.⁵⁹ The EU does not see its model of digital strategic autonomy as a closed or inward-looking one. The previously mentioned communication states explicitly:

European technological sovereignty is not defined against anyone else, but by focusing on the needs of Europeans and of the European social model. The EU will remain open to anyone willing to play by European rules and meet European standards, regardless of where they are based.⁶⁰

Openness therefore refers to the EU economic model. The EU market remains open, despite the need of ensuring control of internal digital assets. In a certain way, we could argue that simply by specifying that the EU pursues a model of digital sovereignty *in an open manner*, one implies that normally digital sovereignty claims may also lead to a closure of the economic system, as we will see later in section V when discussing the Chinese posture to digital sovereignty. The EU makes it explicit that while its digital sovereignty strategy involves a market intervention, the economic system will remain open to any businesses willing to accept EU rules and standards.

Decision (EU) 2022/2481, which established the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030, listed the general objectives of the Digital Decade. Article 3(c) states that ensuring the Union’s digital sovereignty in an open manner should be achieved by introducing

⁵⁷ Recital 6 (emphasis added).

⁵⁸ European Commission, ‘*Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*’, 2.

⁵⁹ On the point, see Celeste, ‘*Digital Sovereignty in the EU: Challenges and Future Perspectives*’.

⁶⁰ European Commission, ‘*Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*’, 2.

secure and accessible digital and data infrastructures capable of efficiently storing, transmitting and processing vast volumes of data that enable other technological developments, supporting the *competitiveness* and sustainability of the Union's industry and economy, in particular of SMEs, and the resilience of the Union's value chains, as well as fostering the start-up ecosystem and the smooth functioning of the European digital innovation hubs.⁶¹

The Decision mainly reiterated the points made in the 2020 communication *Shaping Europe's Digital Future*: the resilience of EU digital infrastructures is key to the development of the EU strategic autonomy in the digital field. Yet, the Decision also adds that digital sovereignty aims to foster the *competitiveness* of the EU in such a domain. This implies that EU economic actors play in an open economic system, where non-EU business can freely compete.

Similarly to the expression 'digital sovereignty in an open manner', the meaning of the concept of 'resource efficient and fair economy' has to be reconstructed from a plurality of different policy instruments. A 'Resource efficient Europe' was a flagship initiative of the Europe 2020 Strategy.⁶² It aimed to foster a shift towards a less resource and energy intensive economy across all sectors. The EU Commission acknowledged the unsustainable character of the current economic model which exploits natural resources and generates high carbon emissions. Efficiency is seen as a way to preserve the current economic framework based on growth, while going greener and enhancing industrial and societal resilience. Making the EU more efficient in terms of exploitation of natural resources, favouring locally available assets, and in terms of energy production as well as a consumption should also be regarded as the European solution to alternative economic models, which have recently advocated more radical solutions based on 'degrowth' or 'sobriety'.⁶³

In the *Shaping Europe's digital future* communication, 'fair and competitive economy' was defined as

a frictionless single market, where companies of all sizes and in any sector can compete on equal terms, and can develop, market and use digital technologies, products and services at a scale that boosts their productivity and global competitiveness, and consumers can be confident that their rights are respected.

The communication does not seem to distinguish between EU and non-EU companies, although it is possible to understand that the actors to which it refers are all established or operate in the single market. The concept of 'fairness' is encapsulated in a vision that see all businesses competing 'on equal term'. A context of 'competitiveness' is explicit both with reference to the internal market and to the global dimension.

Codagnone et al. collected the legislative initiatives pursuing the objective of a 'fair and competitive economy' mentioned by the 'Shaping Europe's digital future' communication.⁶⁴ They included: the proposal of the European Data Act, which aims to

⁶¹ Decision 2022/2481, Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030.
Ibid.

⁶² European Commission, 'Europe 2020 Strategy', 14.

⁶³ See Jan Pollex and Andrea Lenschow, 'Surrendering to Growth? The European Union's Goals for Research and Technology in the Horizon 2020 Framework', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Technology and Degrowth, 197 (1 October 2018): 1863–71; Céline Péréa, Jessica Gérard, and Julien de Benedittis, 'Digital Sobriety: From Awareness of the Negative Impacts of IT Usages to Degrowth Technology at Work', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 194 (1 September 2023): 122670, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122670>.

⁶⁴ Cristiano Codagnone et al., 'Europe's Digital Decade and Autonomy' (European Parliament, October 2021), [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695465/IPOL_STU\(2021\)695465_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695465/IPOL_STU(2021)695465_EN.pdf), 34.

unlock the potential of industrial data, particularly in the context of Internet of Things and connected devices;⁶⁵ the Data Governance Act, which seeks to foster the availability and use of data across key economic sectors;⁶⁶ the revision of the Database Directive of 1996, which is seen as an essential tool to foster the use of personal and non-personal data by AI systems;⁶⁷ the Digital Services Act regulating online platforms;⁶⁸ the Digital Markets Act, which imposes obligation on online ‘gatekeepers’;⁶⁹ the proposal of a digital levy, which would guarantee a fairer tax imposition;⁷⁰ and finally a legislative initiative on new design requirements and consumer rights for electronics, which connects digital policies with green transition objectives mandating a series of obligations in terms of eco-design of smartphones and other digital devices.⁷¹ In the context of fair competition, Codagnone et al. emphasized that the first EU legislative initiative regarding online competition was the Regulation on platform-to-business relations (P2B Regulation) of 2019, which establishes rules for a trustworthy business environment for small companies and traders on online platforms.⁷² What all these initiatives have in common is their objective to foster a digital economy where a level playing field for all actors is guaranteed, or in other words a ‘fair and competitive economy’. Some of them will be analysed in more detail in the next section as they also possess elements that aim to enhance the EU strategic autonomy in the digital field.

IV. The EU regulatory framework towards digital strategic autonomy

A. EU digital dependence

The EU quest for digital sovereignty intended as strategic autonomy from third country actors stems from a condition of structural dependence. A significant portion of EU data are processed by non-EU companies and EU public and private actors heavily rely on non-EU digital infrastructures. Mayer and Lu define digital dependence as ‘the extent to which actors in a particular country have to rely on foreign-controlled digital technologies to perform digital activities.’⁷³ They propose an index composed of six degrees of digital dependence: from absolute autarky to absolute dependence going through two levels of sensitivity (high

⁶⁵ European Commission, ‘Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)’ COM(2022) 68.

⁶⁶ ‘Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European Data Governance and Amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)’, 152 OJ L § (2022).

⁶⁷ Marie-Astrid Huemer, ‘Revision of Directive 96/9/EC on the Legal Protection of Databases |’ (European Parliament, October 2021), [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)694232](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2021)694232).

⁶⁸ ‘Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and Amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)’, 277 OJ L § (2022).

⁶⁹ ‘Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on Contestable and Fair Markets in the Digital Sector and Amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)’, 265 OJ L § (2022)., Chapter III.

⁷⁰ Karoline Kowald, ‘Digital Levy and a Proposal for Digital Levy as Own Resource’ (European Parliament, 2023), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/digital-levy/report?sid=7501>.

⁷¹ European Parliament, ‘New Design Requirements and Consumer Rights for Electronics Pursuant to Directive 2009/125/EC | Legislative Train Schedule’ (European Parliament) <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/spotlight-JD22/file-design-requirements-and-consumer-rights-for-electronics>> accessed 24 November 2023.

⁷² Codagnone et al. ‘Europe’s Digital Decade and Autonomy’, 35; ‘Regulation (EU) 2019/1150 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on Promoting Fairness and Transparency for Business Users of Online Intermediation Services’, OJ L 186 §.

⁷³ Maximilian Mayer and Yen-Chi Lu, ‘Digital Autonomy? Measuring the Global Digital Dependence Structure’, SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 30 March 2023), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4404826>, 2.

and low) and two levels of vulnerability (high and low).⁷⁴ Analysing data from 2019, Mayer and Lu depict a picture of high levels of cross-dependencies between all countries around the world, with the only exception of the US, which display a significant level of resilience, and China and South Korea, which are both characterised by a low level of vulnerability.⁷⁵ This scenario would be the result of decades of globalisation, the general adoption of a neo-liberal approach and deregulation combined with the emergence of a world-wide market for digital technologies.⁷⁶ The digital dependence index proposed by Mayer and Lu allows also to show the absolute ‘autonomy gap’ between the best and the worst performing country in terms of digital autonomy, with Brazil, Saudi Arabia and Australia among the nations with the highest difference from the US.⁷⁷ In the last ten years, a group of countries, including China, South Korea, the US and Russia, have been successful in increasing their level of digital autonomy, while states like Mexico, Turkey, Indonesia and Japan increased their level of structural dependence in the digital field.⁷⁸

The EU as a bloc presents a critical level of digital dependence vis-à-vis the two global technological epicentres situated respectively in the US and China. On the one hand, the EU is dependent on China in relation to the provision of ICT goods, while, on the other hand, it heavily relies on the US in terms of digital infrastructures.⁷⁹ Mayer and Lu conclude their analysis arguing that the EU regulatory power in the digital field is not sufficient to achieve digital autonomy if not accompanied with ‘infrastructural’ power. They advocate in favour of a more comprehensive and bolder policy approach to digital autonomy. Indeed, in the next section we will explain that the EU has so far invested more in enhancing its regulatory autonomy vis-à-vis foreign actors. However, we will also highlight the timid emergence of regulatory instruments aiming to reinforce the autonomy and resilience of the EU in terms of digital infrastructures. It is exactly in relation to this last category of intervention that our doubts in terms of potential protectionist attitude surface.

B. A twofold regulatory response: from rules to resources

The regulatory response of the EU to its digital dependence has been twofold. On the one hand, the EU has introduced new rules regulating the processing of EU personal data and digital services offered in the EU. This regulatory response has a clear extraterritorial effect and aims to achieve a digital sovereignty in terms of application of EU fundamental rights and values, regardless of the country of origin of the digital actor involved. As we observed earlier in this chapter, this regulatory counteraction is of centrifugal nature, as it exercises a series of regulatory effects beyond EU borders. On the other hand, a second regulatory trend is currently emerging, this time generating a centripetal force which aims to reattract the production of digital products and services within the EU and to rely on EU digital infrastructures.

The first regulatory response of the EU aims to extend, consolidate and exploit the EU capacity to introduce normative standards, both internally, harmonising EU member states’ approaches to digitalisation, and internationally, by exercising what Anu Bradford defined as

⁷⁴ Ibid, Table 2.

⁷⁵ Ibid, Figure 2.

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Ibid, Figure 4.

⁷⁸ Ibid, Figure 7.

⁷⁹ Ibid.

the *de jure* and *de facto* ‘Brussels effect’.⁸⁰ To this end, the European Union’s institutions have been working at full steam. The broad movement to create an ‘Europe fit for the digital age’ is regarded by Papakonstantinou and De Hert as a process of ‘actification’.⁸¹ The authors explain that the European Commission’s new preference for the term ‘act’ is linked to the objective of raising public awareness of the EU normative power, regardless of the absence of ‘acts’ as legal sources in EU treaties.⁸² This strategy has been pursued with the adoption of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Governance Act, the Digital Services Act (DSA), the Digital Market Act (DMA), and the Cybersecurity Act.⁸³

The GDPR, which regulated data protection across the EU and was adopted in 2016, does not explicitly mention digital sovereignty as an aim; yet, its provisions on extraterritorial scope of application (Article 3) and international data transfers (Articles 45 ff.) aim to ensure that the application of EU data protection standards is not circumvented by the mere fact that the entity processing personal data is located outside the EU or that data are transferred to non-EU countries. The GDPR aims to ensure that in both these cases EU data protection law will apply, thus – we could say – preserving EU sovereignty over its personal data.

The Cybersecurity Act is a regulation adopted in 2019. It institutionalised the role of ENISA, the EU cybersecurity agency, and introduced an EU cybersecurity certification mechanism. The European Economic and Social Committee, in its 2018 opinion on the proposed regulation, underlined that the new act’s objective of establishing an EU cybersecurity competency network is in line with the EU digital sovereignty ambitions.⁸⁴ The network aims to connect the actors of the EU cybersecurity value chain. In this way, the Committee argues, the network will help reduce the EU dependency from the technical skills of other countries and ultimately boost the EU competitiveness in the cybersecurity sector.

The Data Governance Act, which was adopted in 2022 and entered into force in September 2023, aims to foster the access and re-use of data – both personal and non – across strategic sectors in the EU. Similarly, the Data Act, entered into force on 11 January 2024, aims at harmonizing the regulation over data access and usage for the benefit of citizens, public administrations, and companies, and complements the Data Governance Act to harness the value of data to boost the European economy. In its first recital of the Data Governance Act, the regulation refers to the objective of avoiding market distortions, enhancing the ‘open strategic autonomy’ of the EU while encouraging transnational flow of data. Here again we see this idea of ‘open’ digital sovereignty: a trend that aims to protect EU values, boost digitalisation while preserving an open economy.

The DSA and DMA too, which were enacted in 2022, do not explicitly refer to digital sovereignty.⁸⁵ However, in both cases, the EU aims to establish rules to preserve digital rights

⁸⁰ Theodore Christakis, “European Digital Sovereignty”: Successfully Navigating Between the “Brussels Effect” and Europe’s Quest for Strategic Autonomy’, SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 7 December 2020), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3748098>, 11; Bradford, ‘The Brussels Effect’; see also Cagnin et al., ‘Shaping and Securing the EU’s Open Strategic Autonomy’, 12.

⁸¹ Vagelis Papakonstantinou and Paul De Hert, ‘The Regulation of Digital Technologies in the EU: The Law-Making Phenomena of “Act-Ification”, “GDPR Mimesis” and “EU Law Brutality”’, *Technology and Regulation* 2022 (21 May 2022): 48–60, <https://doi.org/10.71265/2hvw3h73>, 49.

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ See Decision 2022/2481, Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030.

⁸⁴ Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the ‘Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on ENISA, the “EU Cybersecurity Agency”, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013, and on Information and Communication Technology cybersecurity certification (“Cybersecurity Act”) COM(2017) 477 final/2 2017/0225 (COD).

⁸⁵ Yet, we can find a reference to digital sovereignty in the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on ‘Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Single Market For

in the context of online platforms and so-called ‘gatekeepers’ that are offering their services in the EU. Most of these services are provided by companies based outside the EU, thus seeking to protecting the European digital environment and preserve the capability of the EU to regulate it.

Finally, one of the most recent texts is the AI Act, which was approved on 13 March 2024. The AI Act is the first comprehensive regulation of AI, providing developers and deployers the requirements of AI while supporting the production of trustworthy AI systems. A core objective of the AI Act and the related policy package is the protection of fundamental rights. The regulation shall apply not only to businesses established in the EU but also abroad which is a continuation of the approach taken from the GDPR.⁸⁶ In fact, since 2021, the Commission stressed the importance of the initiative to preserve the EU digital sovereignty.⁸⁷

Despite the absence of explicit references to digital sovereignty ambitions, in all these cases, the EU adopted a regulatory framework to de facto promote digital sovereignty not much to reduce its economic digital dependence from other countries, but to ensure that, even if heavily relying on foreign digital infrastructures and services, EU digital rights standards are preserved. Digital sovereignty as a strategic autonomy in terms of values rather than in relation to resources. Yet, more recently, this last aspect has been addressed in a second strand of regulatory reactions promoted by the EU, which ultimately aims to reinforce Europe’s independence from third countries in terms of supply of digital products.

As an alternative to the European dependency in the field of semiconductor chips, which represent an essential component of digital devices, the EU adopted the Chips Act, officially entered into force on 21 September 2023.⁸⁸ The Act is part of the European Chip Strategy, which possesses five strategic objectives: 1) to strengthen EU research and technology leadership; 2) to build and reinforce the EU own capacity to innovate in the design, manufacturing and packaging of advanced chips, and turn them into commercial products; 3) to put in place an adequate framework to increase substantially EU production capacity by 2030; 4) to address the acute skills shortage, attract new talent and support the emergence of a skilled workforce; and finally 5) to develop an in-depth understanding of global semiconductor supply chains.⁸⁹

The objective of a stronger EU semiconductor industry does not mean complete self-sufficiency, which is not attainable. This was also recognised by the European Commission President von der Leyen when presenting the Chip Act.⁹⁰ The plan is to double the EU’s semiconductor production by 2030, reaching twenty per cent of world production, as stated in the 2021 Digital Compass communication and 2022 Digital Decade Policy Programme. The commitment of increasing the semiconductor production is explicitly linked to a perceived ‘European dependency on supply from a limited number of companies and

Digital Services (Digital Services Act) and amending Directive 2000/31/EC’ COM(2020) 825 final — 2020/0361 (COD) 2021.

⁸⁶ ‘Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 Laying down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence and Amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA Relevance)’, OJ L 2024/1689 §.

⁸⁷ Ibid.

⁸⁸ ‘Regulation (EU) 2023/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 Establishing a Framework of Measures for Strengthening Europe’s Semiconductor Ecosystem and Amending Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Chips Act) (Text with EEA Relevance)’, 229 OJ L 229 § (2023).

⁸⁹ Ibid.

⁹⁰ European Commission, ‘Statement by the President on the European Chips Act’, Text, European Commission, 8 February 2022, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/statement_22_866.

geographies, and its vulnerability to third country export restrictions and other disruptions in the present geopolitical context'.⁹¹ Recital 15 of the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 also stresses the importance of semiconductors to the green transition.⁹²

The explanatory memorandum attached in the proposal of the Act states that European stakeholders invest mainly in Research and Development (R&D) but that this is not translating into industrial benefits.⁹³ It recognises that the EU is well positioned in the fields of design of semiconductors components for power electronics, radio frequency and analogues devices, sensors and microcontrollers that are used in the automotive and manufacturing industries, but lags behind in the design of digital logic (processors and memory), which are essential for data, AI and connectivity development. In this context, Codagnone et al. highlight the EU twofold dependency on the US for chip design and on Asian countries for the production of semiconductors, while globally member states have a position of leadership in specific fields, such as sensors and automotive semiconductors.⁹⁴ The entry costs to the chip production market for EU businesses appear to be prohibitive; hence, chip fabs are in the hands of a monopoly of firms, including the Taiwanese TSMC and South Korean Samsung.⁹⁵ EU businesses rather seem to specialise in specific phases of the production process.⁹⁶

More concretely speaking, the EU Chips Act envisages to tackle this situation by operating in three areas. Firstly, it introduces norms to regulate the so-called 'Chips for Europe Initiative', which consists in facilitating the knowledge exchange from EU laboratories to chip fabs, by promoting the creation of pilot production lines, a cloud-based design platform, competence centres and the establishment of a Chips Fund for industrial investors.⁹⁷ Secondly, it introduces a normative framework to foster public and private investments in integrated production facilities and so-called 'Open EU Foundries'. Special rules are introduced to allow EU countries to grant state aids to these productive infrastructures.⁹⁸ Thirdly, the Act establishes a coordination and monitoring mechanism, the European Semiconductor Board, connecting the Commission to Member States. Such a system will oversee the demand and production of semiconductors and will activate a crisis stage through an alert system in case of critical shortages.⁹⁹ It will be complemented by the Chips Joint Undertaking, an entity which replaces the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and that will manage funds under the Horizon Europe or DEP programmes to foster the Chips for Europe Initiative.¹⁰⁰

Deeply rooted in the need to overcome dependency and the risk of disruption in supply chains, the EU Commission also proposed the Critical Raw Material Act in September 2023. The Act follows the declaration adopted at the margin of the 2022 informal meeting of

⁹¹ European Commission, Proposal For A 'Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council Establishing A Framework Of Measures For Strengthening Europe's Semiconductor Ecosystem (Chips Act) ('COM(2022) 46 final 2022/0032(COD) <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0046>> accessed 24 December 2023, 1.

⁹² Decision 2022/2481, Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030.

⁹³ European Commission, Proposal for a Chips Act, 1.

⁹⁴ Codagnone et al. 'Europe's Digital Decade and Autonomy', 22.

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Articles 1(1)(a), 3 to 12, respectively.

⁹⁸ Articles 1(1)(b), 14, 15, 16 and 18, respectively.

⁹⁹ Articles 28 to 32 respectively.

¹⁰⁰ 'Council Regulation (EU) 2023/1782 of 25 July 2023 Amending Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 Establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe, as Regards the Chips Joint Undertaking', OJ L 229 §.

EU governments held in Versailles that highlighted the role of critical raw material for the ultimate goal of strategic autonomy and sovereignty of the EU.¹⁰¹ In the notes accompanying the proposal, the Commission stressed the importance of this legislation to address concerns regarding reliance on third country suppliers. The proposal contains a set of measures to guarantee access to the supply of critical raw materials which are critical for several strategic sectors, including technology.¹⁰² As part of this strategy, in 2022 the EU also concluded a Digital Partnership with Singapore. The project aims to jointly shape the digital field through rules and standards harnessing their power to boost their digital economy allowing businesses to operate across borders.¹⁰³ The EU-Singapore Digital Partnership targets the semiconductor supply chain, promoting private investment in order to safeguard security and resilience amidst the global technological race.¹⁰⁴

Finally, in October 2023, the EU Commission adopted a recommendation on critical technology areas for the EU's economic security, as part of the European Economic Security Strategy.¹⁰⁵ It encourages Member States to carry out a collective impact assessment with the Commission on four technology areas that, on the one hand, possess a significant technological potential, but, on the other hand, might have a military use, thus threatening global peace, or might be used to violate fundamental rights. Namely: advanced semi-conductor technologies, AI technologies, quantum technologies and biotechnologies. The Commission is expected to launch ancillary initiatives in this domain by spring 2024.¹⁰⁶ Yet, it is possible to observe a further consolidation of the coupling between EU strategic autonomy and security concerns in the digital field.

V. Comparative perspectives: US and Chinese regulatory strategies

A. United States: from clean energy to digital autonomy

The EU is not alone in the race towards digital sovereignty. This trend is shared with other states around the world. Japan, Taiwan, South Korea, the United States and China are the main competitors.¹⁰⁷ It goes without saying that, despite they all have different levels of development and areas of focus in the digital industry, their digital economies are deeply intertwined as the result of international trade and industrial cooperation.¹⁰⁸ However, it seems that what once was a fruitful network of alliances for development, it is today the root of global geopolitical tensions in the field of technology. The COVID-19 pandemic, recent

¹⁰¹ European Council, 'The Versailles Declaration, 10 and 11 March 2022', Consilium, 11 March 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/03/11/the-versailles-declaration-10-11032022/7>.

¹⁰² European Commission, 'European Critical Raw Materials Act', Text, European Commission, 16 March 2023, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_1661.

¹⁰³ European Commission, 'EU-Singapore Digital Partnership', 1 February 2023, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/eu-singapore-digital-partnership,1>.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid, 5

¹⁰⁵ European Commission, 'Commission Recommendation of 03 October 2023 on Critical Technology Areas for the EU's Economic Security for Further Risk Assessment with Member States' C(2023) 6689 final; see also European Commission, 'Joint Communication "European Economic Security Strategy"', JOIN(2023) 20 final.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ Gary Clyde Hufbauer Hogan Megan, 'Major Semiconductor Producing Countries Rely on Each Other for Different Types of Chips', Peterson Institute for International Economic, 31 October 2022, <https://www.piie.com/research/piie-charts/major-semiconductor-producing-countries-rely-each-other-different-types-chips>.

¹⁰⁸ Jakob Edler et al., 'Technology Sovereignty as an Emerging Frame for Innovation Policy. Defining Rationales, Ends and Means', Research Policy 52, no. 6 (1 July 2023): 104765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104765..>

wars and economic tensions acted as a warning to all these nations.¹⁰⁹ They all realised how dependent they have become on each other.¹¹⁰ Consequently, most of these countries have introduced regulations and policies modifying their technological industry. Harnessing power to secure strategic autonomy as an expression of digital sovereignty is the current global motto. The United States vs China's rivalry is the epitome of these geopolitical tensions in the digital field.¹¹¹ It is claimed that both countries have adopted a techno-nationalist vision that is driving the implementation of industrial policies aiming at digital self-sufficiency, leaving behind the supply chain vulnerabilities, while driving out foreign competitors.¹¹² This competition has even acquired 'cold war' nuances, deeply affecting bilateral trade.¹¹³

The United States has unfolded its own strategy which targets its competitors while strengthening its internal industrial forces. In recent policies and regulations, the US seems to have relinquished the multilateral free-market rules, for a more stringent position relying on subsidies as well as domestic benefits.¹¹⁴ The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) and the Creating Helpful Incentives to Procure Semiconductors and Science Act (CHIPS Act) are two recent pieces of legislation intended to increase private investments, address supply chain and national security concerns as well as reducing carbon emissions.¹¹⁵ Concretely, both laws put in place a package of incentives for investments in clean energy productions and semiconductor manufacturing.¹¹⁶

It is clear then that this kind of 'America First' approach, which started with President Trump, continues now under the Biden administration and it is part of a major turn in the US digital sovereignty competition against foreign influence, with particular attention to China.¹¹⁷ The rationale behind such rules is to address the national security risks that either Chinese technological companies operating in the United States or Chinese-developed technology implemented nationally represent for the country.¹¹⁸ By combining both regulations, the US

¹⁰⁹ Ibid.

¹¹⁰ 'Vermessung Der Digitalen Dependenz', Digital Dependence Index, accessed 25 March 2025, <https://digitaldependence.eu/en/>.

¹¹¹ Yadong Luo and Ari Van Assche, 'The Rise of Techno-Geopolitical Uncertainty: Implications of the United States CHIPS and Science Act', *Journal of International Business Studies* 54, no. 8 (1 October 2023): 1423–40, <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41267-023-00620-3>.

¹¹² Paul Evans, 'Techno-Nationalism in China–US Relations: Implications for Universities', *East Asian Policy* 12, no. 02 (April 2020): 80–92, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793930520000161>; see also Vivek Mishra, 'The Great U.S.-China Tech Decoupling: Perils of Techno-Nationalism', *orfonline.org*, accessed 25 March 2025, <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-great-u-s-china-tech-decoupling>

¹¹³ Alex Capri, 'US-China Decoupling in Tech', *Hinrich Foundation*, 4 June 2020, <https://www.hinrichfoundation.com/research/wp/tech/us-china-decoupling-tech/>.

¹¹⁴ Luo and Van Assche, 'The Rise of Techno-Geopolitical Uncertainty', 1424.

¹¹⁵ Luis A. Abad, Donald C. Hok, and Brianna C. Sullivan, 'What the Inflation Reduction and CHIPS Acts Could Mean for US Importers', *The Tax Adviser*, 1 June 2023, <https://www.thetaxadviser.com/issues/2023/jun/what-the-inflation-reduction-and-chips-acts-could-mean-for-us-importers/>.

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

¹¹⁷ Christian Scheinert, 'EU's Response to the US Inflation Reduction Act (IRA)' (European Parliament - Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, June 2023) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_IDA\(2023\)740087](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_IDA(2023)740087); see also Luo and Van Assche, 'The Rise of Techno-Geopolitical Uncertainty', 1426.

¹¹⁸ Agathe Demarais, 'How the U.S.-Chinese Technology War Is Changing the World', *Foreign Policy* (blog), 26 March 2025,

aim at not only creating but increasing a demand for locally manufactured semiconductors, considering that the clean energy sector (electric vehicles, wind turbines and solar panels) relies on this technology.¹¹⁹ Yet, despite securing digital sovereignty is a legitimate venture, the US regulatory strategy has raised concerns due to its protectionist underpinnings and potential discriminatory effects, which has sparked a chain reaction around the globe.¹²⁰

The Inflation Reduction Act was signed by President Biden on August 16, 2022. The law includes more than 20 modified tax incentives as well as billions of dollars in financial aid programs to increase investment in clean energy technology, and deployment of a clean energy economy. Most importantly, the goal is building a low carbon energy system with American-made technology.¹²¹ Subsidies for electronic vehicle purchase and investment subventions for manufacturers clean-tech products are among the measures offered.¹²² However, the IRA conditioned the benefits offered to the satisfaction of local content requirement, being this one of its most distinctive aspects. Local content requirements are policy measures implemented by countries in international commerce to favour domestic industry over foreign competition with the objective of spurring competitiveness of local industries.¹²³ Consequently, local content requirements are commonly introduced as a condition to use domestically produced goods or services, including a percentage of domestic labour or parts that a good must contain to be sold in a country.¹²⁴ Therefore, in order to fulfil the local content requirement of the IRA, all the steel or iron used in a structural function must be mined, produced or manufactured in United States' soil.¹²⁵ Likewise, measures such as the consumer tax credit on electric vehicles could reduce the cost of eligible cars, but

<https://foreignpolicy.com/2022/11/19/demarris-backfire-sanctions-us-china-technology-war-semiconductors-export-controls-biden/>.

¹¹⁹ Poorva Karkare, 'Unpacking Digital Sovereignty through Industrial Policy', in *Global Approaches to Digital Sovereignty: Competing Definitions and Contrasting Policy*, ed. Melody Musoni, Poorva Karkare, and Ennatu Domingo, Discussion Paper No. 344 (The Centre for Africa-Europe Relations, 2023), <https://ecdpm.org/application/files/7816/8485/0476/Global-approaches-digital-sovereignty-competing-definition-s-contrasting-policy-ECDPM-Discussion-Paper-344-2023.pdf>.

¹²⁰ Nicholas Crawford, 'The Energy Transition, Protectionism and Transatlantic Relations', *Survival* 65, no. 2 (4 March 2023): 75–102, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00396338.2023.2193101>.; see also Abad, Hok and Sullivan, 'What the Inflation Reduction and CHIPS Acts Could Mean for US Importers'. Not only the European Union has reacted to the US recent strategy, now even countries such as Japan are openly considering strengthening their own industries via tax incentives. See: Kantaro Komiya, 'Japan Eyes Tax Break for Domestic EV Battery, Chip Production - Nikkei', Reuters, 11 August 2023, sec. Technology, <https://www.reuters.com/technology/japan-eyes-tax-break-domestic-ev-battery-chip-production-nikkei-2023-08-11/>.

¹²¹ The White House, 'Clean Energy Economy: A Guidebook to the Inflation Reduction Act's Investments in Clean Energy and Climate Action', 2023, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Inflation-Reduction-Act-Guidebook.pdf>, 9.

¹²² David Kleinman et al., 'How Europe Should Answer the US Inflation Reduction Act' (Bruegel, 9 February 2023), <https://www.bruegel.org/policy-brief/how-europe-should-answer-us-inflation-reduction-act>.

¹²³ Jan-Christoph Kuntze and Tom Moerenhout, 'Local Content Requirements and the Renewable Energy Industry - A Good Match?', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 12 September 2012), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2188607>, 5.

¹²⁴ Michael Lind, 'The Case for Domestic Sourcing', *American Compass* (blog), 9 June 2020, <https://americancompass.org/on-domestic-sourcing/>.

¹²⁵ Brent Sabot, Debbie Gordon, and Heather Rosas, 'New Treasury Guidance on IRA Domestic Content Rules', RSM (blog), 19 May 2023, <https://rsmus.com/insights/tax-alerts/2023/new-treasury-guidance-on-ira-domestic-content-rules.html>.

would result in a large disadvantage and loss of export to those companies manufacturing vehicles not included in the benefited list.¹²⁶

What is more relevant about the law is the inconsistency of the local content requirements with the existing international trade rules of the WTO, even disregarding basic principles such as non-discrimination, in violation of the most-favoured-nation (MFN) principle.¹²⁷ In the context of the international trading system, according to the MFN principle there cannot be any discrimination between the trading partners of the different countries, meaning that there is no place for special benefits or conditions towards a specific country over others.¹²⁸ Likewise, the MFN principle provides an equalitarian treatment in terms of tariffs, internal taxes and internal regulation to all trading partners.¹²⁹ Consequently, with the introduction of the local content requirements and tariffs, the US are disregarding settled principles in international trade potentially discriminating foreign producers. It remains to be seen the course of action of foreign countries to this measure that may affect trade as it has been known until now.

In August 2022, the CHIPS Act was enacted with the aim of fostering manufacturing, strengthening supply chain and enhancing domestic research as well as development of local capabilities.¹³⁰ Just as the IRA, the CHIPS Act introduces a series of new grants, tax credits and other incentives focused on the manufacturing and supply chain located in the US. Overall, the CHIPS Acts provides for: (i) the Advanced Manufacturing Investment Tax Credit (AMITC) equivalent to 25% of the qualified investment in the construction of manufacturing facilities; (ii) the CHIPS for America fund, which is a competitive based grant mechanism to fund investments in facilities and equipment in the different stages of manufacturing of semiconductors as well as research; and, (iii) the CHIPS for America Workforce and Education Fund, which provides funds for workforce development activities ranging from training to apprenticeships.¹³¹

It all boils down to the desire of boosting investment in the American semiconductor sector and making the US self-sufficient, reducing the likelihood of a chip supply interruption due to a global crisis or foreign sabotage.¹³² The semiconductors need to be made in America. Additionally, the CHIPS Act not only intends to invest in the local semiconductors industry, it

¹²⁶ Kleinman et al., 'How Europe Should Answer the US Inflation Reduction Act', 2, 6, 8; see also Scheinert, 'EU's Response to the US Inflation Reduction Act (IRA)', 8.

¹²⁷ Kleinman et al., 'How Europe Should Answer the US Inflation Reduction Act', 9; Scheinert (n 101); Kleimann et al, 'EU's Response to the US Inflation Reduction Act (IRA)', 9.

¹²⁸ World Trade Organisation, 'Principles of the Trading System', accessed 25 March 2025, https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/fact2_e.htm.

¹²⁹ William J. Davey, 'Non-Discrimination in the World Trade Organization' (Brill, 2012), <https://brill.com/display/title/21953>, 67; see also Tobias Naef, Data Protection without Data Protectionism : The Right to Protection of Personal Data and Data Transfers in EU Law and International Trade Law (Springer Nature, 2023), <https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/96229>, 245 246.

¹³⁰ Matt Furlow, 'What's the Status of the CHIPS and Science Act Implementation?', U.S. Chamber of Commerce (blog), 28 August 2023, <https://www.uschamber.com/technology/chips-and-science-act-anniversary-progress-made-but-work-remains>.

¹³¹ Bruce J. Kessler, 'State Tax Credits and Incentives Under the IRA or CHIPS Act', Deloitte United States, 2022, <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/tax/articles/chips-act-state-tax-incentives.html>.

¹³² Vishnu Kannan and Jacob Feldgoise, 'After the CHIPS Act: The Limits of Reshoring and Next Steps for U.S. Semiconductor Policy' (Carnegie Endowment for International Piece, 22 November 2022), <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2022/11/after-the-chips-act-the-limits-of-reshoring-and-next-steps-for-u-s-semiconductor-policy?lang=en>; Abad, Hok and Sullivan, 'What the Inflation Reduction and CHIPS Acts Could Mean for US Importers'.

also limits ongoing investments and the growth of the semiconductor manufacturing sector in China. It addresses so by prohibiting companies in receipt of any CHIPS Act incentives to engage for a 10-year period in substantial transactions that could support the material expansion of China's capacity in the semiconductors' field as well as any other country of interest.¹³³ In sum, both instruments set aside internationally agreed trade rules to achieve industrial autonomy in the race for digital sovereignty.

B. China's ambitions towards 'de-americanisation'

For several years, China has been working towards achieving self-sufficiency to finance and control the growth of its technology industry.¹³⁴ Its regulatory efforts are mainly materialized in "Made in China 2025", a national plan drafted by the Ministry of Industry and Information (MIIT) in 2015.¹³⁵ Inspired by Germany's "Industry 4.0" plan,¹³⁶ China introduced this programme to accelerate its manufacturing capacities, promoting the development of advanced and traditional industries as well as modern services.¹³⁷ Since 2014, this policy has been accompanied by financial aids through state funding, such as the "National Integrated Circuit Industry Investment Fund" as well as additional State Council policy documents that furthered down the objectives to strengthen the technological industry such as Document No. 8.¹³⁸ Likewise, the 14th five-year economic plan (2021-2025) of the government declared the semiconductor industry a national priority in 2020, with the firm objective of achieving self-sufficiency.¹³⁹ Self-sufficiency being understood as a semiconductor supply chain controlled by China and serving the needs of the domestic market.¹⁴⁰ Overall, the Chinese strategy to achieve self-sufficiency relies on the idea of reducing vulnerabilities due to the interdependence with the US, which is also perceived as a "de-americanisation" of supply chains.¹⁴¹

The Made in China 2025 (MIC) plan is the most renowned Chinese policy program to regain technological power. The goal of MIC is reducing reliance on foreign technology imports while investing in the creation of domestic companies which can compete in global

¹³³ Abad, Hok and Sullivan, 'What the Inflation Reduction and CHIPS Acts Could Mean for US Importers'.

¹³⁴ Gregory C. Allen, 'China's New Strategy for Waging the Microchip Tech War' (Center for Strategic International Studies, 5 March 2023), <https://www.csis.org/analysis/chinas-new-strategy-waging-microchip-tech-war>.

¹³⁵ Scott Kennedy, 'Made in China 2025', Center for Strategic and International Studies, 6 January 2015, <https://www.csis.org/analysis/made-china-2025>.

¹³⁶ Johannes Winter, Anna Frey, and Jan Biehler, 'Towards the Next Decade of Industrie 4.0 – Current State in Research and Adoption and Promising Development Paths from a German Perspective', *Sci* 4, no. 3 (September 2022): 31, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sci4030031>, 3.

¹³⁷ Ibid.

¹³⁸ Nigel Inkster, Emily S. Weinsten, and John Lee, 'Ask the Experts: Is China's Semiconductor Strategy Working? - China Dialogues', *China Dialogues - A Platform for Discussion and Collaboration among Leading China-Watchers* (blog), 1 September 2022, <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/cff/2022/09/01/is-chinas-semiconductor-strategy-working/>.

¹³⁹ Allen, 'China's New Strategy for Waging the Microchip Tech War'; see also Kirana Aisyah, 'China Expanding Digital Economy for Tech Self-Sufficiency – OpenGov Asia', *OpenGov Asia*, 12 November 2021, <https://opengovasia.com/2021/11/12/china-expanding-digital-economy-for-tech-self-sufficiency/>.

¹⁴⁰ Christopher Thomas, 'Lagging but Motivated: The State of China's Semiconductor Industry', *Brookings*, 7 January 2021, <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/lagging-but-motivated-the-state-of-chinas-semiconductor-industry/>.

¹⁴¹ Evans, 'Techno-nationalism', 82.

markets.¹⁴² The MIC conceives an innovation-driven manufacturing sector which would integrally upgrade the industry sector, improving the global position of China in the supply chain.¹⁴³ Despite this policy programme is described as a comprehensive industrial plan – thus implying an integrated programme in the military and civil sector –¹⁴⁴ the first prioritized area is “New generation IT industry” targeting core general purposes chips.¹⁴⁵

Regarding semiconductors, the MIC introduced a shift from previous policies by proposing to acquire foreign technologies via mergers and acquisitions (M&A).¹⁴⁶ Indeed, one of the tools to implement MIC is increasing Chinese M&A transactions abroad, acquiring foreign makers of advanced automated equipment to attract technologies to China and reduce the number of foreign competitors.¹⁴⁷ For instance, following MIC, there was a surge of Chinese M&A transactions in Germany in key sectors, such as cars with alternative driving technology, biomedicine and robotics.¹⁴⁸ Likewise, in 2016, the value of Chinese M&A operations in the US surpassed USD 45 billion.¹⁴⁹ At the same time, MIC aimed at attracting foreign investments in manufacturing fields, such as new generation IT, high-end equipment, new materials among others.¹⁵⁰ Additionally, MIC promoted the use of foreign investments not only in the introduction of technology but also in the development of joint ventures and development of the Chinese manufacturing industry.¹⁵¹ In fact, the efforts of the Chinese government to attract foreign investments into the country continue; for instance, the Ministry of Science and Technology proposed simplified approval procedures for foreign-invested research and development centres and simplified procedures for the cross-border transfers of IP and technologies among others.¹⁵²

Among its specific guidelines, the MIC sets goals to secure the positioning of local companies in the semiconductors market.¹⁵³ For instance, the MIC seeks an increase by 40% the participation of Chinese vendors in the core components market and up to 70% of

¹⁴² Institute for Security & Development Policy, ‘Made in China 2025’, June 2018, <https://www.isdp.eu/publication/made-china-2025/>.

¹⁴³ Kennedy, ‘Made in China 2025’.

¹⁴⁴ Evans, ‘Techno-nationalism’, 82.

¹⁴⁵ PCR State Council, ‘Notice of the State Council on the Publication of Made in China 2025’, trans. Ben Murphy (Center for Security and Emerging Technology, 8 May 2015), https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/t0432_made_in_china_2025_EN.pdf.19.

¹⁴⁶ Thomas, ‘Lagging but motivated’.

¹⁴⁷ Marilia Bassetti Marcato, ‘The Made in China 2025 amid Hyperglobalization: Upgrading, Intangible Assets, and Internationalization Strategies’, *Economia e Sociedade* 31 (29 July 2022): 355–84, <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-3533.2022v31n2art05>, 364.

¹⁴⁸ Cora Jungbluth, ‘Is China Systematically Buying Up German Key Technologies?’, *Global & European Dynamics* (blog), 22 May 2018, <https://globaleurope.eu/globalization/is-china-systematically-buying-up-german-key-technologies/>.

¹⁴⁹ James McBride and Andrew Chatzky, ‘Is “Made in China 2025” a Threat to Global Trade?’, *Council on Foreign Relations*, accessed 19 December 2023, <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/made-china-2025-threat-global-trade>.

¹⁵⁰ PCR State Council, ‘Notice of the State Council’, 25.

¹⁵¹ *Ibid*, 31.

¹⁵² Lewis Lu, ‘China Continues Efforts to Attract Foreign Investment’, *International Tax Review*, 28 March 2023,

<https://www.internationaltaxreview.com/article/2bgm3ajcqdaq2szn77z0g/local-insights/china-continues-efforts-to-attract-foreign-investment>.

¹⁵³ Renato Balderrama Santander and Amado Trejo Romero, ‘Made in China 2025 and Self-Sufficiency in New Technologies.’, *Revista Comercio Exterior Bancomext*, accessed 19 December 2023, <https://revistacomercioexterior.com/span-langen-usmade-in-china-2025-and-self-sufficiency-in-new-technologies>.

participation for important basic materials.¹⁵⁴ Moreover, the MIC established a percentage of Chinese content materials in sectors such as smartphone processors, industrial robots and equipment's necessary for renewable energy generation.¹⁵⁵

The National Integrated Circuit Industry Investment Fund, dubbed as the “Big Fund”, was put in place in 2014 and it is one of the financial vehicles to subsidize the semiconductor Chinese domestic industry.¹⁵⁶ The fund, which was renewed in 2019, provides state funding for domestic semiconductor industry, state-driven acquisitions overseas and procurement of foreign semiconductor equipment.¹⁵⁷ The Big Fund had a capitalization of USD 28.9 billion back in 2019 and, just in October 2023, it invested USD 1.99 billion in Changxin Xinqiao, a memory chip company.¹⁵⁸ The national financial arm of the Chinese self-sufficiency policy is a crucial part to achieve the strengthening of the semiconductor industry.

Moreover, China's State Council issued Document No. 8 to further down the developments made by previous policies in 2000 and 2011.¹⁵⁹ Document No. 8 introduced policies on fiscal, tax, investment, research and development, import and export, talent intellectual property, market application and international cooperation policies.¹⁶⁰ Regarding tax and fiscal policies, Document No. 8 provided most domestic semiconductor companies with financial assistance through a variety of measures such as exemption from import duties and corporate profit taxes as well as preferential value-added tax. Some of these exemptions are meant to be valid for up to ten years in certain specifically designated sectors.¹⁶¹ Additionally, China's State Council supported mergers and acquisition across the nation to build a stronger industry.¹⁶² It also encouraged the use national and local investment funds, while also inviting local governments and commercial financial institutions to grant business loans.¹⁶³ In relation to intellectual property, China's State Council proposed companies to register for exclusive rights on integrated circuit designs and software copyrights.¹⁶⁴ This move has been accompanied by additional measures which require certain specified patents and intellectual property to be owned by independent Chinese companies, which are China-based and without possibility to be owned or controlled outside of China.¹⁶⁵

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ Ibid.

¹⁵⁶ Allen, ‘China's New Strategy for Waging the Microchip Tech War’.

¹⁵⁷ Karen Suttler, ‘China's New Semiconductor Policies: Issues for Congress’, legislation, 20 2021, <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/R46767>, 4.

¹⁵⁸ Ibid.

¹⁵⁹ ‘China Stresses High-Quality Development in Integrated Circuits and Software’, The State Council of the People's Republic of China, 4 August 2020, https://english.www.gov.cn/policies/latestreleases/202008/04/content_WS5f2956b4c6d029c1c26373f1.html.

¹⁶⁰ PCR State Council, ‘Notice of the State Council’, 2-8.

¹⁶¹ Allen, ‘China's New Strategy for Waging the Microchip Tech War’.

¹⁶² PCR State Council, ‘Notice of the State Council’, 3.

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Ibid, 6.

¹⁶⁵ ‘Answers to Questions about the “Notice on the Relevant Requirements for the Preparation of a List of Integrated Circuit Enterprises or Projects and Software Enterprises That Enjoy Tax Incentives”’, National Development and Reform Commission, 31 March 2021, https://www.ndrc.gov.cn/xxgk/jd/jd/202103/t20210331_1271319.html.

VI. Conclusion: Towards a test to limit digital protectionism

The similarity in the regulatory and policy strategies deployed by the US and China is apparent. Both countries have implemented instruments to strengthen their techno-industrial sector and they do so through protectionist measures, by increasing the assistance of the state while leaving foreign competitors in an uneven playfield. Despite the process of the US and China is the result of years of tension, this overprotective trend affects countries around the world. Indeed, the EU has acknowledged that the strategies deployed by both countries have triggered a chain reaction of ‘geopolitical, economic, and technological global rivalry’.¹⁶⁶ Against this backdrop, can we speak of a form of digital protectionism emerging throughout the EU digital sovereignty strategy presented in the previous sections? And if yes, what can the EU do to prevent this risk?

As it happens to other concepts of the digital sphere, there is no universal consensus on the definition of digital protectionism among policy makers.¹⁶⁷ In particular, the US regards digital protectionism as an ‘erection of barriers or impediments to digital trade, including censorship, filtering, localization and regulations to protect privacy’.¹⁶⁸ In line with this definition, back in 2017, the US Trade Representative labelled as protectionist actions of Russia, China, the EU, and Turkey.¹⁶⁹ However, the American perspective clarifies that the EU’s digital sovereignty quest differs from those emerging in Russia, China and Turkey because of the techno-authoritarian aspect present in those countries, stressing that the European vision is based on protecting the interest of individuals.¹⁷⁰

Yet, concretely speaking, it can be argued that the EU concerns justifying its digital autonomy strategies do not differ from the justifications given by other countries, such as China and the US. In fact, as was discussed in the previous section, the rationale behind both countries’ measures is the self-protection against external risks.¹⁷¹ In light of this, there are conflicting positions regarding the qualification of European policies and regulation as protectionist. Bradford claims that it is more plausible to say that EU strategies are ‘tough regulation’ rather than protectionist measures, considering the lack of hard evidence and the difficulty to detect the protectionist strain in these kinds of programmes.¹⁷² Conversely, other authors argue that EU regulations such as the GDPR, despite commendable, also imply protectionist aspects or just plainly assumes EU regulatory framework is protectionist.¹⁷³

Looking at the various conceptualisations of digital protectionism, it is undeniable that the EU has decided to safeguard its own industry and citizens. The recent EU Chips Act, the Data Act and the recently approved AI Act are reflects a defensive position of the EU. There have been even cooperative initiatives of Member States enacting measures to strengthen technological sovereignty through export restrictions, as it recently happened in

¹⁶⁶ European Commission, ‘2023 Strategic Foresight Report’, 2.

¹⁶⁷ Susan Ariel Aaronson, ‘What Are We Talking about When We Talk about Digital Protectionism?’, *World Trade Review* 18, no. 4 (October 2019): 541–77, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1474745618000198>.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid.

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ Frances Burwell and Kenneth Propp, ‘Digital Sovereignty in Practice: The EU’s Push to Shape the New Global Economy’, Atlantic Council (blog), 2 November 2022, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/in-depth-research-reports/report/digital-sovereignty-in-practice-the-eus-push-to-shape-the-new-global-economy/>, 6.

¹⁷¹ See supra section III.

¹⁷² Christakis, ‘European Digital Sovereignty’, 53; Bradford, ‘The Brussels Effect’.

¹⁷³ Tobias Naef, ‘Data Protection without Data Protectionism’ 134; see also Muge Ucar and Altug and Yalcintas, ‘GDPR and Digital Protectionism in the EU: The Cases of Android and iOS’, *Journal of Economic Issues* 57, no. 4 (2 October 2023): 1079–94, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00213624.2023.2273120>.

the Netherlands.¹⁷⁴ The objective of these pieces of legislation or policies is to foster local industry development and upholding European standards. Nonetheless, the adoption of such an allegedly protectionist approach would come with a cost. There are fears that Europe would develop its own techno-nationalism,¹⁷⁵ excluding overseas competitors in the internal market to benefit European companies.¹⁷⁶ This has raised the question of whether the EU is following the so criticized Chinese path in implementing overprotective measures.¹⁷⁷ Such protectionist policies and regulations could amount to a violation of international trade law, as it has happened with recent US actions.¹⁷⁸ There is also the likelihood that, if not carefully applied, programs which grant excessive benefits to European businesses, either in services or manufacturing, could constitute unlawful discrimination, disregarding WTO principles.

Protectionist measures would also impact on the possibility of revitalising the cooperation channels between the US and the EU.¹⁷⁹ Some regulations could be self-defeating; for instance, the Data Act and other restrictions which aim to foster opportunities for European firms may hinder European companies' opportunities to compete globally.¹⁸⁰ It could be even contradictory to impose restrictions or additional burdens to European businesses to access foreign technology, as this not only translates in rising costs and performance alterations but also it could slow down the desired technological advancement for the region.¹⁸¹ Furthermore, protectionist policies can also take a toll on consumers because they cause higher prices to be paid and impact product safety.¹⁸²

The main concerns that have driven the EU to deploy a policy and regulatory strategy with a protectionist tone are beyond discussion. Nonetheless, this chapter argues that the focus should be on the middle to long term effects that such measures could cause in the economic horizon of the Union. It would be relevant to introduce a necessity and proportionality test to identify less economically distorting solutions, while preserving the protection of fundamental rights, which should represent the other key guiding principle of EU digital sovereignty policies.¹⁸³ Every current and future regulatory instrument in the context of the digital sphere should be preceded by a detailed assessment that balances out its objectives with its effects. The EU must safeguard European business and citizens without causing a major disruption to the dynamics of the single market and its original vision founded on an open economic model.

¹⁷⁴ Sara Poli, 'Reinforcing Europe's Technological Sovereignty Through Trade Measures: The EU and Member States' Shared Sovereignty', *European Papers - A Journal on Law and Integration* 2023 8, no. 2 (27 July 2023): 429–45, <https://doi.org/10.15166/2499-8249/665>; for more instances of national restrictive measures on digital matters see also Janka Oertel, 'China: Trust, 5G, and the Coronavirus Factor', in *Europe's Digital Sovereignty: From Rulemaker to Superpower in the Age of US-China Rivalry*, ed. Carla Hobbs (European Council of Foreign Relations, 2020), https://ecfr.eu/publication/europe_digital_sovereignty_rulemaker_superpower_age_us_china_rivalry/.

¹⁷⁵ Christakis, 'European Digital Sovereignty', 57-58.

¹⁷⁶ Aaronson, 'Digital Protectionism', 29.

¹⁷⁷ Christakis, 'European Digital Sovereignty'.

¹⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, 60.

¹⁷⁹ Stefan Fölster, 'From Digital Protectionism to Digital Alliances' (Frivärld, 19 April 2023), <https://frivarld.se/rappporter/from-digital-protectionism-to-digital-alliances/>.

¹⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, 11.

¹⁸¹ Christakis, 'European Digital Sovereignty', 63.

¹⁸² Limor Hatsor and Artyom and Jelnov, 'Product Regulation or Protectionism?', *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development* 32, no. 2 (17 February 2023): 266–80, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638199.2022.2081712>, 277.

¹⁸³ See 'Digital Sovereignty in the EU: Challenges and Future Perspectives'; Celeste, 'Digital Constitutionalism, EU Digital Sovereignty Ambitions and the Role of the European Declaration on Digital Rights'.

Global markets on digital technologies are reorganised around the world by overlapping national digital sovereignty strategies.¹⁸⁴ The EU in this context starts the race in a disadvantaged position. The objectives of the EU are in principle different from those of the US and China. Digital sovereignty ambitions should not be merely motivated by economic reasons but should be informed by the need to protect fundamental digital rights in the EU. While from an economic perspective it might make sense for the EU to adopt a realistic approach focusing on specific areas where a concrete improvement in terms of digital autonomy can be achieved,¹⁸⁵ from a legal perspective digital sovereignty policies and regulatory strategies should be assessed primarily – not to say, exclusively – against the need to preserve digital fundamental rights.

Digital protectionism, if pushed at the level the US and China did in their digital autonomy policies, may violate international trade law. The EU should pre-emptively assess its digital sovereignty strategies using a necessity and proportionality test against the need to protect EU digital values and principles. There, once again, the EU will have the opportunity to demonstrate if it is only a ‘union of merchants’ or rather really a ‘union of rights’.

¹⁸⁴ Andrea Ciani and Michela Nardo, ‘The Position of the EU in the Semiconductor Value Chain: Evidence on Trade, Foreign Acquisitions, and Ownership’ (European Commission, 2022), <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129035>, 5.

¹⁸⁵ See Codagnone et al., ‘Europe’s Digital Decade and Autonomy’, 60.